

Table 1. Performance of Liangyou Peite in South China and Hunan provincial and regional trials.

Character	South China		Hunan	
	1991	1992	1992	1993
	Mid 23 sites, 10 provinces	Late 12 sites, 8 provinces	Mid 7 sites	Mid 6 sites
Growth duration (d)	143.0	125.9	136.7	135.8
Growth duration (d) over check	-1.5	-3.4	-3.0	-5.5
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	6.2 ^a	6.7	9.5	7.7
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹) over check	1.6 ^b	8.9 ^c	4.7 ^{bd}	5.8 ^b
Basic tillers (no. m ⁻²)	99.0	-	145.5	136.5
Maximum tillers (no. m ⁻²)	478.5	-	559.5	603.0
Productive panicles (no. m ⁻²)	288	317	333	333
Spikelets (no. panicle ⁻¹)	157.8	132.6	140.1	144.5
Filled grains (no. panicle ⁻¹)	118.6	100.8	126.2	122.3
Seed set (%)	75.2	76.0	87.9	84.6
1,000-grain weight (g)	22.8	23.1	23.4	22.3
Plant height (cm)	101	93	98	106

^aBrown rice yield. ^bCheck is Shanyou 63 (three-line rice hybrid). ^cCheck is Shanyou Gui 99 (three-line rice hybrid).
^dSignificant at the 1% level.

Table 2. Grain quality of Liangyou Peite.

Grain length (mm)	5.28
Grain width (mm)	2.35
Length-width ratio	2.30
Chalky grain (%)	80.0
Chalky area (%)	5.3
Brown rice (%)	83.8
Milled rice (%)	75.9
Head rice (%)	60.0
Gelatinization temperature (°C)	4.8
Gel consistency (mm)	30
Amylose content (%)	22.4
Protein content (%)	10.3
Eating quality	Good
Remark on quality	Fine

for making indica and japonica hybrid rices. The male parent Teqing is a high-yielding inbred indica variety.

The seed yield of Pei' Ai 64 S averaged more than 3.0 t ha⁻¹ with a maximum of 5.5 t ha⁻¹. F₁ hybrid seed yield was 2.3-3.0 t ha⁻¹ in Hunan in 1995. ■

Khushboo, a quality rice cultivar for Rajasthan

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BK-805-36, a cross derived from Baran Basmati/Pusa 150, has been released as Khushboo in Rajasthan, India. It was identified in the F₆ generation at ARS, Kota.

Khushboo is a semidwarf cultivar that matures in 118-123 d when transplanted. It is suitable for either normal or late sowing and possesses ideal plant type with upright leaves, compact tillering, late leafsenescence, and horizontal flag leaf position. Panicles are long (28 cm), compact, and fully exerted. Spikelets are partially awned and straw colored. Kernels are 7.5 mm with a length-breadth ratio of 4.7.

Table 1. Performance of Khushboo in varietal trials. Kota, Rajasthan, India. 1986-91.

Year	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		CD (0.05)
	Khushboo	Basmati 370 (check)	
1986	3.4	2.6	0.4
1987	3.5	2.8	0.5
1988	2.9	2.1	0.3
1989	2.7	2.3	0.5
1990	3.5	3.0	0.3
1991	4.0	3.4	0.4
Average	3.3	2.7	
Percent over Basmati 370	23.9		

Kernel length after cooking is 13.4 mm with an elongation ratio of 1.8. The grains are long and slender, white, translucent, and strongly scented. Cooked rice is soft and well separated.

In trials conducted at Kota from 1986 to 1991, Khushboo yielded consistently higher than Basmati 370 (Table 1). In coordinated trials conducted during 1989 at 11 locations and in 1990 at 7 locations, Khushboo yielded 14.7 and 9.17% more than Basmati 370, respectively. In on-farm demonstrations conducted, Khushboo yielded 41% in 1991 and 54% higher than Basmati 370 (Table 2).

The cultivar is resistant to leaf blast and sheath rot, and moderately resistant to neck blast, brown spot, and white-backed plantopper. ■

Table 2. Khushboo grain yield in on-farm demonstrations. Kota, Rajasthan, India. 1991-92.

Year	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	Khushboo	Basmati 370 (check)
1991 (4 locations)	4.9	3.5
Percent over Basmati 370	41	
1992 (7 locations)	3.9	2.5
Percent over Basmati 370	54	

Bright-pearl 1, a fast grain-filling japonica rice

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All of the traditional late-japonica rice cultivars grown in the Yangtze River area of China require 45-50 d from heading to ripening. Sometimes the grain-filling period is longer because of unfavorable weather, resulting in low rice yield and delayed sowing of the next crop. Local farmers normally choose early-ripening rice cultivars. But the plants usually have insufficient growing time.

With a longer vegetative stage and a fast grain-filling rate, the late-japonica rice can be harvested in late October instead of early November, thus avoiding inclement weather and reducing moldy or sprouted seed. Using a fast grain-filling cultivar can increase rice quality. The ability to supply the market early means a better price for growers.

Bright-pearl 1, derived from Bin 8103/713 in 1992, is a fast grain-filling japonica rice. Its grain filling is 10-15 d faster than that of check Xiushui 11. Bin 8103 is an early ripening/japonica cultivar resistant to brown planthopper (BPH) and blast. 713 is